

The Effect of the Foreign Political Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Domestic Political Processes

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Abstract: This is it in the article Uzbekistan Republic of external political strategy and his country internal political processes effect seeing will be released . Uzbekistan to independence from what he achieved after international on the field position strengthening in order to done being increased external politics country inside economic, social and political to reforms effect is showing . In particular , diplomatic communications , investments attraction to do and external political cooperation internal stability and reforms done increase for main factors is happening Also in the article of Uzbekistan international organizations with cooperation , geopolitical factors and regional to safety directed external political directions internal political to the environment effect analysis will be done.

Keywords: external politics, internal politics, Uzbekistan, international organizations, investments, diplomatic relations, reforms, geopolitics, regional safety.

Sign in . State external policy how much successful take from going , his internal economic and political stability too is provided . For example , foreign investments attraction to do of the state internal economy to strengthen service does. Investments new work seats creates technologies and modern management to the country take includes , this and own in turn , economic to development reason will be External economic of communications expansion internal markets strengthens and of the state financial to the system his own positive effect shows .

Also the state international political and geopolitical strategy internal political to stability directly effect is enough Peace and security to provide directed regional cooperation internal political stability in the environment provides. For example , regional safety according to next door countries with together take went politics instability risk to reduce help gives. And this internal political reforms stable done to increase the ground creates.

Cultural external as well politics internal to development his own positive contribution adds. International cultural exchanges countries between mutually cultural dependence strengthens it while internal national unity to strengthen help gives of the state international scale cultural in projects participation reach national of culture the world to be recognized on stage possibility gives. As a result , the national pride and citizenship solidarity increased , internal political processes and reforms successful will pass

Summary by doing in other words , of the state external political strategy only international to relationships not but internal integral to development depends . External of politics success country inside political stability, economic development and cultural rise provide for main of the factors is one That's it because of , har how state own external policy internal goals and interests with harmonized without take to go necessary

Uzbekistan Republic to independence from what he achieved since own external political strategy formation and to develop big attention looking at is coming External of politics main purpose of Uzbekistan sovereignty and national interests international on the field protection do , regional and global security provide , economic to development contribution to add and of the country international authority from raising consists of This to goals reach for done being increased external politics internal political to processes too effect showing is coming

External politics and internal economic reforms : of Uzbekistan external in politics main from directions one international economic connections expand and foreign people investments attraction is to do President Shaukat Mirziyoyev to the authorities coming with this process more activated . In particular , Uzbekistan the world Bank , International currency fund (IMF) and Asia development bank such as international organizations with cooperation internal economic reforms for financial help source being service is doing These reforms internal of the economy stable growth in providing important importance occupation is doing

Foreign investors with cooperation and international financial organizations with connections internal political stability in storage important place holds In particular, investors confidence win for in the country legal reforms done increasing , this while political the system to modernize help is giving

Geopolitical position and regional security: of Uzbekistan geopolitical position , that is Central in Asia location his regional in security important role to play take will come External of politics main from the goals one this security is to provide . in Afghanistan instability and international terrorism danger Uzbekistan external political strategy in formation solution doer factors it has been . Uzbekistan of the government next door countries with good relationships installation and safety in the field cooperation internal political stability in storage help is giving

International organizations with of cooperation internal political effect : of Uzbekistan international organizations with cooperation is also internal political to processes positive effect is showing. For example, United Nations Organization (UN), Shanghai cooperation Organization (SCO), Europe safety and cooperation Organization (OSCE) and another international organizations with connections country inside political and social reforms in acceleration important factor is happening by the UN before pushed a person rights and democratic principles Uzbekistan internal in politics important place occupied in the country citizenship society to develop help is giving

Cultural diplomacy and internal national unit : of Uzbekistan external in politics cultural diplomacy is also special place holds. Foreign countries with cultural exchange and international scale cultural events of the country internal national unity to strengthen service is doing Uzbekistan people for common cultural of inheritance international recognition in the field national the pride in raising important factor as service does And this internal political stability more to strengthen help is giving

Conclusion: Uzbekistan Republic of external political strategy country internal political processes significant level effect is showing. International relations , geopolitical cooperation and investments attraction to do such as external political directions internal political reforms and stability in storage important factors being service is doing That's it with together , cultural diplomacy and international organizations with cooperation country inside political of the system modernization and democratic principles in strengthening important role is playing of Uzbekistan external political strategy international on the field position strengthening with together , internal political processes are also positive effect in showing continue is doing

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